

the lowest population; cartap and decamethrin + buprofezin had moderate populations. Ethoprofos granules applied 20 DT did not restrict WBPH multiplication at booting; populations on that plot were higher than in the control.

Insecticides applied 70 DT significantly reduced WBPH populations. Carbofuran (1.0 kg ai/ ha) and cartap (1.5 kg ai/ha) were most effective, followed by decamethrin + buprofezin (0.09 kg ai/ ha) and chlorpyrifos (0.5 kg ai/ha) spray. □

Residues of monocrotophos in rice

H. K. Senapati, S. K. Mohanty, M. R. Pattnaik, and A. K. Pal, Pesticide Residues Laboratory, Soils and Agricultural Chemistry Department, Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology, Bhubaneswar 751003, India

We studied residues of monocrotophos (3-[dimethoxy phosphinyl oxy]- N -methyl-cis-crotonamide), a common pesticide, in rice variety Lalat (ORS26-2014). The pesticide was sprayed at the recommended level (0.05%, or 0.25 kg ai/ ha) and double the recommended level (0.1%, or 0.50 kg ai/ ha). Triplicate plant samples were collected at 0, 10, 20, and 30 d after spraying and at harvest.

The spectrophotometric method was used to estimate residues of monocrotophos, using p-nitrobenzyl pyridine as the chromogenic reagent. Recovery of monocrotophos from fortified samples was 83.2-84.5%.

Mean initial residues of 10.97 ppm (0.05%) and 19.91 ppm (0.01%) were reduced to 3.26 and 5.19 ppm 10 d after pesticide application, to 1.14 and 2.11 ppm 20 d after application, and to nondetectable levels 30 d after application. Dissipation was 89.5% for both application levels 20 d after application.

Rate of degradation with both application levels seemed to follow the first-order reaction (see figure). Fifty percent of the toxicant was reduced at

Linear plot of first-order reaction of monocrotophos in rice. Bhubaneswar, India.

2.4 d at 0.05% application level and at 2.3 d at 0.1%. The safe waiting period (T_{tol}) was 17.8 d and 19 d.

Grain and straw samples had nondetectable levels of monocrotophos. □

Preliminary observations on *Entomophthora delphacis*

Li Hongke, Institute of Plant Protection, Hunan Academy of Agricultural Sciences, Changshu, China

The pathogen *E. delphacis* of brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* is an important entomogenous fungus widely distributed in irrigated ricefields of South China. It attacks mainly BPH, whitebacked planthopper, and small brown planthopper. It also infects zigzag striped leafhopper and green leafhopper (GLH).

E. delphacis usually are most abundant during the overcast and rainy season. In later growth stages of long-duration rice. Infection percentages reach 70-80% when temperatures are 10-

20 °C (day-night) with relative humidity more than 90%. In the Changsha region, the numbers of BPH infected by *E. delphacis* ranged from 37% to 64%. In 1985, a year of high humidity, infection reached 69.7%. In 1986, a dry year, infection was only 27.3%.

We used a fungus suspension on artificial media and naturally infected insects for bioassay to determine virulence on BPH and GLH in the laboratory. Results are presented in the table. Mortality of naturally infected insects was higher than that of artificially infected insects. □

Virulence of *E. delphacis* in the laboratory. Changsha, China.

Pathogen source	Insect tested	Insects (no.)	Mortality (%) after infection		
			2 d	4 d	6 d
Natural	BPH	139	22.8	53.3	68.3
	GLH	92	18.0	32.4	61.1
Artificial ^a	BPH	120	6.3	18.4	31.2
	GLH	120	2.7	11.3	24.3
Control (water)	BPH	110	1.8	1.8	2.7
	GLH	73	2.7	2.7	2.7

^a Sabouraud's agar + egg yolk.

Toya spp. planthopper incidence on *Brachiaria mutica*

P. Baskaran, M. Jayanthi, and G. Shankar, Entomology Department, Faculty of Agriculture, Annamalai University, Annamalaiagar 608002, India

Brachiaria mutica, cultivated in about 15 ha at the Annamalai University Sewage Farm, exhibited severe hopperburn symptoms in Feb 1986 and again in Oct. Investigations revealed abundant numbers of a planthopper.

The delphacid resembles brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens*, except that it is smaller. Both brachypterous and macropterous forms were seen in large numbers Oct-Dec 1986: smaller numbers are seen throughout the year.